

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF CONSTRUCTION OF THE VOLT-CURRENT CHARACTERISTICS OF A PHOTOELECTRIC CURRENT SOURCE

Salamov O.,

Institute of Radiation Problems of NAS of Azerbaijan,

Leading Researcher

Doctor of Philosophy in Physics, Associate Professor

Aliyev F.

International Eco-Energy Academy,

Doctor of Philosophy in Engineering

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7752748](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752748)

Abstract

The paper presents a method for calculating the current-voltage characteristic (CVC) of a solar photovoltaic current source (PCS). The influence of external factors, such as the temperature of the environment and surfaces of photocells (PC), illumination conditions, contamination of their surface, etc., is considered. on the output parameters, especially on the values of the short-circuit current and load current, at the point of maximum CVC power, no-load voltage and load voltage at the point of CVC maximum power, as well as the maximum PCS power allocated at the optimal load. The equivalent circuit of the PC, their total CVC, as well as a simplified circuit for taking the CVC of the PC are given.

Keywords: photocell, photovoltaic current source, solar radiation, short circuit current, load current, no-load voltage, load voltage, maximum power, ambient temperature, lighting conditions.

1. Introduction

As you know, all domestic methods of generating electricity, with the exception of the use of hydroelectric stations, are carried out using liquid, gaseous or solid fuels, the reserves of which are declining every year. In addition, the use of domestic fuels leads to the release into the environment of various types of calorific gases, leading, in the upper atmosphere, to the "greenhouse effect" and an increase in the average temperature of the globe, ultimately causing various types of cataclysms (floods, global drowning, uncharacteristic climatic conditions, tsunamis, acid rain, etc.). Therefore, since the middle of the last century, the world's leading scientists have come to a unanimous conclusion that it is necessary to abandon the use of domestic fuels, especially those used for heat and power supply, as soon as possible [1]. In this aspect, special attention is paid to the use of environmentally friendly and inexhaustible energy sources, as well as the production of new types of synthetic fuel. These energy sources primarily include solar, wind, geothermal and wave energy, as well as biomass energy, the energy of small rivers, tides, etc., among which, in terms of scale and availability, solar energy is the most promising because it is everywhere and always available. Solar energy can be used both for heat supply and for electricity supply. To convert solar energy into electrical energy, multi-stage and single-stage (direct) conversion methods are used. With multi-stage conversion at the first stage, the radiant energy of the sun, with the help of focusing mirrors, is reflected and concentrated on the base and side walls of the boiler installed on the tower. At the same time, the coolant is heated to a critical (over 500°C) temperature and pressure (20-25 MPa). Further, all processes occur in the same way as in thermal and nuclear power plants. Both parabolic (dish-shaped) and parabolic-cylindrical concentrators are used as focusing mirrors. efficiency power plants of this type is relatively high, but due to the need for precise orientation

of all concentrators to the sun, their cost is also high [2]. To directly convert solar energy into electrical energy, various types of photoconverters are used. The most widely used of them are single-crystal, polycrystalline and amorphous silicon photoconverters. efficiency depends on many factors, which are discussed below.

2. General characteristics of PC and PCS assembled on their basis

As you know, after release, PC are subjected to laboratory tests, which are carried out under standard testing conditions. However, in real conditions, completely different indicators are obtained, which should be taken as the main ones. Since when powering a device from a PCS, only real operating conditions should be taken into account. In this case, one should take into account both climatic conditions and the possibility of optimal matching of the PCS with the load at different values of the solar radiation intensity (SRI). To achieve this goal, it is necessary to take into account the correct choice of the number of PC and series-connected PC and solar modules (SM), at the time of PCS assembly based on them [3,4].

A relatively strong external factor influencing the operating modes of PC and PCS, in general, is the ambient temperature. The higher the PC surface temperature, the lower the energy generated by them. In addition, the operating modes of the PC and SM are significantly affected by the temperature power factor (TPF), as well as the type of device powered by the PCS. For example, if $TPF=0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$ is indicated in the PCS passport data for TPF, this means that with each increase in the PC temperature by 1°C , relative to the standard temperature (25°C), its power decreases by 0.4%. And this means that, taking into account the indicated value of TPF, at a temperature of 40°C , the developed power of the PC, as well as SM and PCS, are reduced by 6%. In most cases, in the summer season, the SM surfaces heat up to 65°C , due to which the work efficiency, as well as

the amount of energy generated, are significantly reduced. So, with the value of TPF - 0.4% °C, heating the surface of the SM to 65°C leads to a decrease in its output power to

$$16\%: P_{out} = [-0,4 \cdot (65 - 25)] = -16\%.$$

It has been experimentally established that, despite the relatively low TPF values of single-crystal PC, their degradation rate is much higher compared to polycrystalline PC, and in a year their power output decreases by 3%, and for polycrystalline PC this indicator does not exceed 2%. High-quality PC will be able to operate in the temperature range of -40 + 90°C, but after 15 years of operation, their energy efficiency decreases by 10%, and after 20 years - by 20%.

An increase in temperature also leads to a decrease in the band gap of silicon PC, due to which the magnitude of the reverse saturation current increases, and the energy consumption for the formation of electron-hole pairs decreases. In this case, there is a slight increase in current, and an intensive decrease in the magnitude of voltage and power.

The value of the photocurrent significantly depends on the spectral characteristics of solar radiation and the optical parameters of the material from which the PC are made. In addition, the output parameters are also greatly affected by their lighting conditions. The table shows the degree of influence of the illumination conditions on the energy production of a solar panel (SP) in% [7]. As can be seen, even with light cloudiness, power generation at the SP is reduced by 20-40%.

Influence of the illumination condition on the energy production of the SP in%

Illumination conditions of the tested SP	Energy generation, %
Clear sunny day - PC are installed perpendicular to the incoming sunlight	100
Легкая облачность	60-80
Overcast	20-30
There is a single-layer protective glass - glass and SP are perpendicular	91
There is a two-layer protective glass - glass and SP are perpendicular	84
There is a single-layer protective glass - glass and SP are located at an angle of 45°	64
Artificial lighting - the SP is located on the table	0,4
The room has bright artificial lighting	1,3
Artificial lighting inside the living room	0,2

3. Theoretical aspects of calculating the parameters and reading the CVC of the SP

When the base of the p-n junction of the PC is illuminated, at this junction, passing through the load resistance R_{load} , in the direction, from the electrode with a negative charge (cathode) to the electrode with a positive charge (anode), a reverse photocurrent I_{FC}^{rev} flows, due to which the voltage drops $U_{load} = I_{PC}^{rev} \cdot R_{load}$ on the load resistance.

Figure 1 shows the equivalent circuit of a PC.

Figure 1. PC equivalent

For an open circuit (in the absence of load resistance R_{load}), the value of direct photocurrent I_{PC}^d can be determined from the equation [8-10]:

$$I_{PC}^d = I_0 \cdot \left[\exp\left(\frac{AeU}{kT}\right) - 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

Then, for the case of connecting a load resistance, the resulting current passing through this resistance can be determined from the equation:

$$I_{load} = I_{PC}^d - I_{PC}^{rev} = I_0 \cdot \left[\exp\left(\frac{AeU}{kT}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{PC}^{rev} \quad (2)$$

since the internal current of the p-n junction and the reverse photocurrent have opposite signs relative to each other.

Since there is no load resistance in the idle mode, i.e. the external price is in the open state, while the value of the load current is also reduced to zero and the open circuit voltage is equal to the open circuit voltage:

$$U_{out} = U_{op.cir} = \frac{kT}{Ae} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{I_{PC}^{rev}}{I_0} + 1\right), \quad (3)$$

where: k is the Stefan Boltzmann coefficient ($k = 1.38 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{C/K} = 0.86 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ eV/K}$); e – elementary charge ($e = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ K}$)

Figure 2 shows the families of dark and light CVCs of PCs. As can be seen from Fig. 2, when the PC is illuminated, the active part of the CVCs is in the region with a negative current value and a positive voltage value. Therefore, it is in this region of the CVC that the characteristic points related to the open-circuit voltage ($U_{op.cir}$), short-circuit current ($I_{sh.cir}$) and reverse photocurrent (I_{PC}^{rev}) are given.

In Figure 2, the value of the maximum power P_{max} , allocated at the optimal load resistance, is equal to the area of the rectangle with sides I_{max} and U_{max} (shaded part).

In this case, the maximum power allocated to the optimal load resistance is determined from the following expression:

$$P_{\max} = \dot{I}_{\max} \cdot U_{\max} = \left\{ \dot{I}_0 \cdot \left[\exp\left(\frac{AeU_{\max}}{kT}\right) - 1 \right] + \dot{I}_{PC}^{rev} \right\} \cdot U_{\max}, \quad (4)$$

The power curve $f = P(I, U)$, characterized by equation (4), depending on the current and voltage, according to the following conditions, acquires a maximum value:

$$\left(\frac{dP}{dU} \right) \Big|_{\dot{I}=\dot{I}_{\max}, U=U_{op.cir}} = 0, \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Family of dark and light CVC of PC

By solving this equation, we obtain the following parameters:

$$\dot{I}_{\max} = -\frac{\dot{I}_{PC}^{rev}}{1 + \frac{1}{A \cdot U_{\max}}} \approx -\dot{I}_{sh.cir} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{A \cdot U_{\max}} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$U_{\max} = \frac{kT}{e} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\frac{\dot{I}_{PC}^{rev}}{\dot{I}_0} + 1}{1 + A \cdot U_{\max}} \right) \approx U_{op.cir} - \frac{kT}{e} \cdot \ln(1 + A \cdot U_{\max}), \quad (7)$$

$$P_{\max} \approx \dot{I}_{sh.cir} \cdot \left[U_{op.cir} - \frac{kT}{e} \cdot \ln(1 + A \cdot U_{\max}) - \frac{kT}{e} \right], \quad (8)$$

From the above systems of equations and analysis, the CVC curves make it possible to determine the extreme values of the main PC parameters. So: $I_{\max} < I_{sh.cir}$; $U_{\max} < U_{op.cir}$; $P_{\max} < I_{sh.cir} \cdot U_{op.cir}$. In accordance with this, the maximum power allocated at the optimal load is .. $P_{\max} = \gamma I_{sh.cir} \cdot U_{op.cir}$. Here γ is the duty cycle of the CVC, which, theoretically, varies within 0.7÷0.8. The higher the value γ , the better the

PC quality is considered, which directly affects the efficiency. both the PCs themselves and the PCS as a whole. Naturally, when moving from PC to SP and from SP to PCS, the numerical value γ decreases, which is characterized by a loss of power due to heat losses, as well as climatic factors and lighting conditions. The following empirical formula is used to determine the numerical value of the duty cycle of the CVC of the SP [10].:

$$\gamma = \frac{P_{\max}}{U_{op.cir} \cdot I_{sh.cir}}, \quad (9)$$

where: $P_{\max}$ - the maximum power of the SP, allocated at the optimal load (in Fig. 2, the shaded part of the light characteristic of the SP, which is equal to $P_{\max} = I_{\max} \cdot U_{\max}$).

Figure 3. Diagram of the stand for removal CVC SP and PCS

Figure 3 shows an experimental scheme for taking the CVC characteristics of individual PCs, as well as PCS. Figure 3: SP-solar panel; R_{load} - variable load resistance (for measurements it is desirable to use a resistance box, type P33, with a maximum limit of up to 99999.9 Ω), A - power ammeter, with a measurement limit of 0-50 A (for more powerful PCSs, the maximum measurement limit of the ammeter should be at least 200 A, and in this case, an appropriate resistance box, potentiometer or modern semiconductor measuring stand should be used); V - multi-stage, digital or pointer voltmeter with the appropriate measurement limit (with a maximum limit for SP 50 V, and for PCS - 100V).

4. Technique for experimental reading of the CVC of the SP

At the Institute of Radiation Problems of the Ministry of Science and Education, a CVC was created with a power of 750 W a SRI of 1000 W/m^2 , which consists of three SPs with a power of 250 W. CVC is built on the facade at the entrance of the institute. In the climatic conditions of Baku, at various values of the SRI, the CVCs of both individual SPs and PCS as a whole were taken. Below is the sequence of the processes of experimental recording of the CVC of the SP [10]:

1. Initially, the load resistance is set to 5 Ω .
2. The SP is installed in the optimal position, which ensures a uniform supply of sunlight on the surface of all PCs.
3. Using a resistance box, (or a modern semiconductor stand, the value of the load current is set closer to the short-circuit current (for a SP, the short-circuit current is 8.77 A, and for a PCS, consisting of three SP - 26.3 A).
4. Measurements of the voltage value on the load resistance were carried out. In this case, the voltmeter scale is preliminarily set to the appropriate limit (for the SP - 50 V).
5. The numerical values of the current and voltage obtained as a result of the measurement were noted in a special table.

6. The load current is determined both by direct measurement, using an appropriate ammeter, and by dividing the voltage drop across the load resistance by the value of this load.

7. Gradually increasing the value of the load resistance, according to the selected step (for the joint venture, with a step of 1.0 V), the voltage drop across the load is also increased, and the results are also noted in the table.

8. Measurements are continued until the voltage value stabilizes.

9. Gradually increasing the value of the load resistance, a decrease in the value of the ammeter in increments of 0.5 A was achieved. At the same time, the values of resistance, current and voltage were recorded each time. This process is continued until the ammeter indicator approaches zero, and the voltage approaches the open circuit voltage.

10. Using the numerical values of the current and voltage obtained from the measurements, the CVC of the SP was built.

11. With resistance values of 0.1 Ω , 1.0 Ω , 10 Ω , 100 Ω , etc. determined, respectively, 5-6 voltage values on the load resistance. Further, using Ohm's law, for each case, the values of the load current are determined and the CVC is plotted.

12. Having determined from the table the maximum values of the load current and voltage on the load, on their basis the maximum power of the SP was calculated.

Figure 4 shows a family of theoretical ones (taken using data obtained from calculations using formulas (1-8), without taking into account thermal and other types of losses, such as contamination of the SP surfaces, inaccurate matching of the CVC of individual PCs among themselves, honest shading of the SP surface, inaccurate matching with an external load, etc.) of one SP, taken at SRI values of 900 W/m^2 (curve 1) and 400 W/m^2 (curve 2). From the CVC characteristics shown in Figure 4, it is possible to determine the optimal values of the resistance of the external circuit, i.e. load resistance, which, for SRI 900 W/m^2 and 400 W/m^2 , are 4.12 Ω and 9.1 Ω , respectively. Further, using these CVC (see Fig. 4) from formula (9) we determine the numerical value of the filling factor of the CVC of the SP, which for the SP we use is $\gamma = 0.757$.

The value of the optimal load resistance of the SP depends on the SRI non-linearly. This is more clearly seen from Figure 5, which shows the graphical dependence of the optimal resistance of the external circuit (load) of the SP on the SRI. As can be seen, the larger the SRI, the smaller the optimal value of the resistance of the external circuit becomes. In addition, from Fig. 4 we determine the following main parameters of the CVC of the SP: $I_{sh.cir} = 7,9$ A; $U_{op.cir} = 37,8$ V; $I_{\max} = 7,00$ A; $U_{\max} = 33,5$ V; $P_{\max} = I_{\max} \cdot U_{\max} = 7,00 \cdot 33,5 = 234,5$ W; $\gamma = 234,5 / (7,9 \cdot 37,8) = 0,785$ (at SRI 900 W/m^2) и $I_{sh.cir} = 3,51$ A; $U_{op.cir} = 37,5$ V; $I_{\max} = 3,1$ A; $U_{\max} = 33,3$ V; $P_{\max} = I_{\max} \cdot U_{\max} = 3,10 \cdot 33,3 = 103,2$ W; $\gamma = 103,2 / (3,51 \cdot 37,5) = 0,784$ (at ISR

400 W/m²). As can be seen, in ideal cases, the numerical value γ , depending on the SRI, almost does not

change. Therefore, in such cases, all kinds of losses are reduced to a minimum.

Figure 4. Theoretical CVC of the SP, taken without taking into account various types of loss: curves 1 and 2 are taken, respectively at RFI 900 W/m² and 400 W/m²

Figure 5. Graphical dependency external resistance circuit (load) SP on the value of SRI

To determine the magnitude of the short circuit current, you can also use the following empirical formula:

$$I_{sh.cir} = I_{sh.cir}^{man} \cdot \lambda \quad (10)$$

where, $I_{sh.cir}^{man}$ - the value of the short-circuit current determined by the manufacturer under standard testing conditions (at SRI 1000 W/m² and surface temperature SP 25°C), A; λ - coefficient showing the ratio of the real value of the SRI value available at the place of the experiment, to the value established by the manufacturer of the SP under standard conditions (1000 W/m²). Thus $\lambda = I_{sh.cir} / I_{sh.cir}^{man}$.

Since the surface temperature of the SP is a strongly influencing factor on its output parameters, taking this into account, using the following formula, it is possible to determine the numerical values of this temperature for various ambient temperatures [6]:

$$T_{SP} = T_{abm} + \lambda \cdot E \cdot (T_{SP}^{nom.op} - 20), \quad (11)$$

where, E - is the value of SRI at the place of the experiment, W/m²; T_{abm} - ambient temperature, °C; $T_{SP}^{nom.op}$ - nominal operating temperature of the surface

of the joint venture, °C; 20 - ambient temperature corresponding to the operating temperature of the SP, °C.

In addition to the ambient temperature, the SP temperature is greatly affected by air humidity, wind speeds, as well as the conditions for the arrival of SRI on the surface of the SP.

Given the temperature, the open circuit voltage is determined from the equation:

$$U_{op.cir} = U_{op.cir}^{man} - [0,0023 T_{amb} (T_{SP}^{nom.op} - 25)] \quad (12)$$

where, $U_{op.cir}^{man}$ - is the open circuit voltage specified by the manufacturer, V; 25 is the standard temperature of the SP under test conditions, °C.

Equation (12) clearly shows that the voltages of the SP, under the conditions of their actual testing, greatly depend on the ambient temperature and the degree of heating of the PC. The results obtained from the calculations also show that with an increase in the temperature of the PC, the power of the SP, as well as the PCS assembled on their basis, sharply decreases. Ultimately, if we take into account the negative impact on the operating modes of the PC, pollution of their surface, under the influence of atmospheric smog, then the maximum output power of the PC, as well as the PCS, is reduced to 50%, in comparison with the results of the test.

Figure 6. Families of VAC SP, filmed in real operating conditions: curves 1 and 2, removed, respectively at SRI 900 W/m² and 400 W/m²

Thus, the CVC of the SP and PCS, taken in real conditions, are much different from similar characteristics taken in the test mode. For clarity, Figure 6 shows the families of CVCs of the SP, taken under real test conditions, with an SRI of 900 W/m² (curve 1) and 400 W/m².

As can be seen, from a comparison of the theoretical (Figure 4) and practical (Figure 6) load CVC of the SP, in the second case, their output power decreases by about 40%, which is characterized by a similar decrease in the value γ of the CVC fill factor. As for the exact value γ of, it can only be found using data taken from real ones, i.e. practical CVC SP. From the family of CVC presented in Figure 6, we determine: $I_{sh.cir} = 7,0$ A; $U_{op.cir} = 37,3$ V; $I_{max} = 4,95$ A; $U_{max} = 30,5$ V; $P_{max} = I_{max} \cdot U_{max} = 4,95 \cdot 30,5 = 151,0$ W; $\gamma = 234,5 / (7,9 \cdot 37,8) = 0,578$ (at SRI 900 W/m²), and $I_{sh.cir} = 3,0$ A; $U_{op.cir} = 37,0$ V; $I_{max} = 2,2$ A; $U_{max} = 30,4$ V; $P_{max} = I_{max} \cdot U_{max} = 2,2 \cdot 30,4 = 66,9$ W; $\gamma = 66,9 / (3,0 \cdot 37,0) = 0,6$ (with SRI 400 W/m²). In this case, insignificant differences in the values γ for different SRIs are apparently due to the inaccuracy of measuring the parameters of the SP.

To improve the output parameters of the SP and PCS, at high temperatures, halographic heat-shielding films are used, due to which the final value is somewhat reduced. Halographic protective films also successfully protect the SP from degradation and mechanical damage.

Results

1. It has been determined that traditional types of energy resources may be exhausted in the near future, in addition, the use of such energy resources adversely affects the environmental situation. The best way out of this situation is the use of environmentally friendly, re-

newable energy sources, primarily solar energy. Methods for converting solar energy into electrical energy are indicated.

2. The method of theoretical determination of the main parameters of the CVC of the SP, as well as the sequence of taking the family of CVC of the SP at various values of the SRI, is given. For the ideal case, i.e. without taking into account thermal, as well as other types of losses, the values of the short-circuit current, the no-load voltage, the current flowing through the optimal external load (the point of maximum power of the CVCs), the voltage at the point of maximum power of the CVCs, as well as the maximum developed power, for two SRI values: 900 W/m² and 400 W/m². Similar CVCs were also taken for the real case. It was found that in real cases, the output power of the SP is reduced by 40%, in comparison with the ideal case, which are usually set as passport data by the manufacturer of the SP.

3. It is determined that for SRI 900 W/m² and 400 W/m², in the ideal case, the numerical values of the coefficient are, respectively, $\gamma = 0,785$ and $\gamma = 0,784$, i.e. almost does not change, and in real conditions they change slightly and amount to $\gamma = 0,578$ and $\gamma = 0,6$, respectively.

4. Calculation formulas for the theoretical determination of the short-circuit current and open-circuit voltage depending on the ambient temperature and the surface of the SP are given.

5. Using the load voltages and load currents taken from the CVC of the SP, taken at the SRI of 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 W/m², the corresponding values of the optimal resistance of the external circuit were calculated by calculation and the graphic dependence of the load resistance on the SRI was taken. It is determined that, depending on the growth of the SRI value, the numerical value of the optimal load decreases exponentially.

References

1. Renewable energy - ensuring a safer future. Measures to combat climate change. United Nations. Electronic resource: <https://www.un.org/ru/climatechange/raising-ambition/renewable-energy>, 03.03. 2023.
2. Solar thermal power plants (STES) Electronic resource: <https://esfccompany.com/projects/energetika/solnechnye-teplovye-csp-elektrostantsii/>, 03/03/2023.
3. M.M. Koltun. Solar cells. Moscow, Nauka, 1987, 190 p.
4. G. Raushenbakh. Solar Design Handbook. Publisher M: Energoatomizdat, 1983, 360 p.
5. Dash P.K., Gupta N.C. "Effect of Temperature on Power Output from Various Commercially Available Photovoltaic Modules". International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications. 2015, V. 5, No 1, p. 148-151.
6. A.V. Kievets, Y.D. Bay, A.A. Suvorov, A.B. Askarov, A.A. Kim. Study of the variation effect of solar panel temperature on the output characteristics of a solar power station under conditions of partial shadowing. Proceedings of Irkutsk State Technical University 2020, No 24(3), p. 627–638.
7. Technical characteristics of solar panels produced by the plant "Azguntex" Azerbaijan, Baku, 2014, 20 p.
8. O.S. Koval, M.S. Tivanov. Determining the parameters of a solar cell from its light current-voltage characteristic. Bulletin of BSU. Ser. 1. 2012. No. 2, p. 39-44.
9. Rzayeva M.P., Salamov O.M., Kerimov M.K. Modeling to get hydrogen and oxygen by solar water electrolysis. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, 2001, no. 26, p.195-201.
10. Measurement of the current-voltage characteristic of a solar cell. Electronic resource, 03.04.2023. <http://solidstate.karelia.ru/d/manuals/solar.pdf>.
11. Salamov O.M. Accumulation of solar energy using semiconductor photocells. Dissert. work for the degree of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences. Baku, 1990, 141 p.